

Magnetic particles (Fe₃O₄) magnify ion transfer processes at the electrified liquid-liquid interface. Case study: Levamisole detection.

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Abstract

This article describes the effect of non-stabilized magnetic particles Fe₃O₄ (nanoparticles aggregates) addition to the aqueous phase of the polarized liquid-liquid interface (LLI) on the interfacial ion transfer processes. LLI was formed between 1,2-dichloroethane and water solutions (1,2 DCE)|water. The synthesis of Fe₃O₄ particles was achieved by the co-precipitation method, after which their appearance, size of aggregates, and zeta potential were assessed. All electrochemical measurements reported in this study were performed using cyclic voltammetry (CV). We evaluated the effect of pH and the presence of different concentrations of Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles aggregates always initially added to the aqueous phase on tetramethylammonium cation (TMA⁺), and 4-octylbenzenesulfonic acid (OBS⁻) ion transfer. We have found that the addition of Fe₃O₄ particles followed by their precipitation and LLI interface modification leads to

pH dependent magnification of the recorded ionic currents attributed to the cation and anion transfer from the aqueous to the organic phase and *vice versa*. As such, we have plotted the calibration curves of TMA⁺ and OBS⁻ in the concentration range of (10-200 μM) revealing that Fe₃O₄ particles have a significant effect on detection sensitivity, which is dependent on the interaction between Fe₃O₄ particles and the analyte being studied. Finally, we assessed the electrochemical behavior of levamisole at the 1,2-dichloroethane|water interface in the presence and absence of Fe₃O₄ particles.

1. Introduction

Fe₃O₄ magnetic (nano)particles (Fe₃O₄ MPs) are of significant importance in the field of (bio)technological development finding applications in a range of different domains including medical, pharmaceutical, biological, analytical chemistry, or tissue engineering, among others[1–3]. The properties of Fe₃O₄ MPs, like high magnetic saturation, low cytotoxicity, good biocompatibility, and stability in a variety of physiological conditions collectively contribute to the ever-growing interest in this very unique material. Fe₃O₄ MPs can be employed in several ways such as i) cell labeling *in vitro*, tracking, and targeting agents or for cell biology applications to e.g. separate and purify cell populations[4]; ii) tissue repair[5]; iii) magnetic field-guided carriers for localized drug delivery or radioactive therapies[6]; iv) magnetic resonance imaging[7]; v) tumor hyperthermia[8]; or vi) magnetofection[9]. The desired properties of the resulting magnetic particles can be achieved by varying the synthesis methods[3]. In a number of examples, Fe₃O₄ MPs are also used to boost the properties of analytical platforms usually by means of target analytes pre-concentration at the surface of appropriately modified particles[10]

A significant effort was devoted to investigating the charge transfer processes at the interface between two immiscible electrolyte solutions (ITIES) over the last four decades. In parallel to a fundamental understanding of the soft interface structure and properties, many scientists proposed a set of elegant biological and chemical applications, including sensing[11,12], drug delivery[13], or potential-driven liquid-liquid extraction of ions[14]. Since ITIES is a particular type of liquid-liquid interface that can be polarized, many electrochemical methods can be employed to investigate the interfacial charge transfer reactions including cyclic voltammetry, differential pulse voltammetry, amperometry, etc.[15]. These techniques are employed as electroanalytical tools for

detecting organic[16], inorganic[17], and (bio)medical chemical species[18], as well as single hard and soft objects (particles) impacting the liquid-liquid interface as described by Laborda *et al.* in a very elegant review paper[19]. From the electroanalytical point of view, many molecules are difficult to be directly detected with electrochemical configurations based on the solid electrodes (lack of signals originating from the reduction/oxidation processes), but can undergo interfacial ion transfer across the ITIES giving ionic currents[18,20].

To enhance the mass transfer of ions across ITIES and thereby increase the sensitivity of the electroanalytical detection, the interfacial modification is done with (nano)particles/(nano)materials meeting particular properties. One methodology involves the utilization of porous materials or capillaries that act as the ITIES support[21]. Whenever the pore within such material has dimensions less than a few dozen of μm , the pore-to-pore separation assures lack of the diffusion zones overlay for the conventional experimental time scale. ~~and~~ If the ~~position of the~~ LLI interface is located within the pore ingress, or the thickness of the employed support is \ll much lesser as compared with the pore x-y dimensionality, a system can be constructed in which the mass transfer of ions happening across the LLI is governed by a hemispherical diffusion. ~~which~~ This in turn, enhances employed platform electroanalytical properties (e.g. limits of detection, voltammetric detection sensitivity)[21].

The second approach that may affect the interfacial properties of the ITIES directly originates from the adsorption of (nano/micro)particles to the liquid-liquid interface. This may lead to the formation of self-assembled nano/micro-films displaying catalytic/inhibiting properties [22,23]. Many types of nanoparticles and nanomaterials were investigated as the support or modification of the ITIES that were found to affect electron/ion charge transfer processes[24]. The example includes gold[25–28], platinum[29,30], silica[31,32], carbon-nanotubes[33], cobalt[34], silver [35], and Au–Pd core–shell nanoparticles[28] among many other. Conductive particles are usually studied as the “electron highways” catalyzing the redox reactions happening between two redox probes each dissolved in one of the contacting immiscible phases. Recently, magnetic iron oxide particles Fe_3O_4 coated with two different polymers, chitosan (CHI) and diethylaminoethyl dextran (DEAE-D) were studied at an electrified water/1,2-dichloroethane interface[36,37]. It was found, that these particles interact with the LLI undergoing the adsorption process as well as with the studied analytes (ions undergoing interfacial ion transfer reactions). The latter is due to electrostatic (rich and pH-dependend surface properties of Fe_3O_4) and hydrophobic (interactions of

chemical functionalities located within the ion and the Fe₃O₄ capping agents chemical structure) interactions[36]. These interactions are relatively weak and can be controlled by simply changing the chemical composition of the dispersion medium, as such, we envisage that simple experiments can be designed in which the analyte is first adsorbed to the Fe₃O₄ particles followed by their pre-concentration within the interfacial region. Possible obstacles can be attributed to the formation of physical barriers in the form of compactly arranged particles, usually observed as dropping ionic currents[37].

In this paper, we have investigated the effect of non-modified magnetic particles Fe₃O₄ (MPs) on the ion transfer processes at the water|1,2-DCE interface. From an analytical perspective, it is interesting to see how these particles improve the detection sensitivity as studied by cyclic voltammetry. The electrochemical responses originating from the interfacial transfer of TMA⁺ (tetramethylammonium), OBS⁻ (octylbenzenesulfonic acid), and levamisole drug were studied in a broad concentration range at different pH values. We have found, that the amount of Fe₃O₄ particles always initially added to the aqueous phase (or in other words the concentration ratio between the ion undergoing interfacial ion transfer reaction and the Fe₃O₄ particles) significantly affects the current responses.

2. Methods and materials

2.1 Chemicals

Most of the chemicals were used as received from the manufacturer/distributor. Tetramethylammonium chloride (TMACl, >98%, Acros Organics), 4-Octylbenzenesulfonic acid sodium salt (4-OBS, 97%, ALDRICH), levamisole hydrochloride(LEV, ≥99%, chemat) were considered as the model ions (first two) and analyte (levamisole). Iron(III) chloride hexahydrate (FeCl₃.6H₂O, 97%, Sigma-Aldrich), iron(II) chloride tetrahydrate (FeCl₂-4H₂O, 98%, Sigma-Aldrich) were used to prepare magnetic Fe₃O₄ particles (the procedure is described below this section). The salt bis(triphenylphosphoranylidene) ammonium tetrakis(4-chlorophenyl) (BTPPATPBCl) were prepared in our lab by metathesis reaction between equimolar quantities of bis (triphenylphosphoranylidene)ammonium chloride (BTPPACl, 97%, Merck) and potassium tetrakis(4-chlorophenyl) borate (KTPBCl, >98%, Merck) following the protocol described in the

literature[38]. The obtained crystals salts – BTPPATPBCl – were dissolved in 1,2-dichloroethane (1,2-DCE, 99%, Sigma-Aldrich) to obtain a 5 mM concentration, that was used afterwards as the organic phase electrolyte solution. For the aqueous phase with a pH of around 5.5, 10 mM sodium chloride (NaCl, analytical grade, POCh) was used. Britton – Robinson Buffer (BRB) solutions were used as the aqueous phase having a pH of 2, and 10. BRB was a mixture of 10 mM acetic acid (CH₃COOH, 99.8%, ChemPure); 10 mM boric acid (H₃BO₃, for analysis, POCh) ; 10 mM phosphoric acid (H₃PO₄, 80%, ChemPure) and 10 mM sodium chloride. 1 M sodium hydroxide (NaOH, for analysis, POCh) solution was used to adjust the pH of BRB.

2.2. Synthesis of Fe₃O₄ magnetic particles

The magnetic particles Fe₃O₄ (MPs) were synthesized according to the protocols published elsewhere[39,40]: Briefly, an aqueous solution of 3 g of NaOH in 20 mL of water was added under vigorous stirring to a stock solution containing 5.19 g FeCl₃·6H₂O and 1.92 g FeCl₂·4H₂O dissolved in 130 mL of water to obtain a reaction mixture. The resulting particles were separated with a hand magnet and washed, and further redispersed with demineralized water. The concentration of Fe₃O₄ particles was determined by allowing three samples to dry at a temperature of 50°C for three days before weighing them. Afterward, the average concentration was calculated. The unit of Fe₃O₄ particles is mg·mL⁻¹.

2.3. Size and zeta potential measurement

DLS (Dynamic Light Scattering) and electrophoretic measurements were used to determine the size and surface charge of Fe₃O₄ particles, respectively. Zetasizer Nano ZS, Malvern Instruments, UK was used in this respect. Temperature during measurement was 25°C. Measurements were performed at different pH using 10 mM NaCl for pH 5.5, 10 mM BRB buffer at pH 2.0 and 10 mM BRB buffer at pH 10.0. For size and zeta potential measurements, single-use polystyrene cuvettes and folded capillary cells DTS1070 were used, respectively.

2.4. Attenuated total reflectance infrared spectroscopy of Fe₃O₄

The attenuated total reflectance sampling of the Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectra of the synthesized Fe₃O₄ particles was recorded using the Shimadzu IRSpirit instrument equipped with the ATR module. The spectral range was set from 400 to 4000 cm⁻¹. Single spectra was recorded as an average of 50 repetitions.

2.5. Electrochemical experiments

Throughout this work, electrochemical investigations were performed using the AUTOLAB PGSTAT 302 N potentiostat–galvanostat (Metrohm Autolab B.V.,The Netherlands). The electroanalytical techniques were controlled with NOVA 2.1 software. The ITIES polarization was performed with a four-electrode electrochemical setup that has a fixed interface area of 1.13 cm². During the measurements, platinum (Pt) wires were placed in the aqueous and the organic phase (assuring that the contact with only one phase) and these served as the counter electrodes. Silver/silver chloride wires (Ag/AgCl) functioned as reference electrodes and were placed in the Luggin capillaries. Ag/AgCl wires were prepared by Ag wire oxidation in saturated FeCl₃ solution. The cyclic voltammetry (CV) technique was used as a characterization and analytical method in this study. The scan rate was fixed to 0.02 V·s⁻¹ (20 mV·s⁻¹). The x-axis is given in the Galvani potential difference $\Delta_{org}^{aq} \Phi$ (V) scale calibrated using the formal Galvani potential difference of the model ion (TMA⁺) transfer which is 160 mV[41]. A schematic representation of the electrochemical cell used for studying ion transfer reactions in this work is bellowed.

Schem 1. 4-electrode ITIES cell used in the facilitated ion transfer.

3. Results and discussions

3.3. Magnetic particles characterization

The chemical nature of the synthesized magnetic Fe₃O₄ particles was confirmed using ATR-FTIR spectroscopy, as shown in Fig. 1A. The ATR-FTIR spectrum indicates that the obtained

Fe₃O₄ particles display a characteristic set of absorption bands[42]. The analysis indicates that the absorption peak at 537 cm⁻¹ is attributed to the stretching vibration mode associated with the Fe-O bond. The presence of a band around 1636 cm⁻¹ and a broad band centered at 3296 cm⁻¹ indicated the presence of hydroxyl groups (-O-H). The former is indicative of OH-bending, while the latter is indicative of OH-stretching[43,44].

Figure 1. ATR-FTIR spectra of Fe₃O₄ particles (A), Zeta-potential measurement of Fe₃O₄ particles at different pH (B), DLS-based size measurement of Fe₃O₄ particles (C). Conditions for the zeta-potential and size distribution measurements: 10 mM NaCl used for pH 5.5, BRBs used for pH 2.0, and pH 10 (pH adjusted with 1 M NaOH).

Given that the electrochemical study was conducted at pH values of 2.0, 5.5, and 10.0, it is important to ascertain the surface charge of the magnetic particles as presented in Fig. 1B. Zeta potential data are illustrated in Figure S1, based on measurements taken at a concentration of 35.9 μg/mL. The Fe₃O₄ magnetic particles exhibit a positive charge at pH 2.0 that was found to be 6 mV that may facilitate the aggregation processes. At pH 5.5 the zeta potential dropped to around -10 mV, still being far from the value where stable colloidal solution can be obtained. Further, increasing pH to 10 allowed the zeta potential to drop to around -35 mV. The obtained zeta potential values correlate well with the expected results of the size distribution as shown in Figure 1C illustrating the size of Fe₃O₄ MPs aggregates plotted in function of the aqueous phase pH. The representative histograms of size distribution measured at each studied pH are presented in Figure S2. The highest absolute zeta potential value was obtained for Fe₃O₄ magnetic particles dispersed in the aqueous phase at pH 10. At this pH, the Fe₃O₄ MPs exhibited the lowest average size of 2.9 μm ± 0.2 μm. For all studied pH values the resulting size of the aggregates was found in between 3 and 5 μm. The smallest (but still large) aggregates with an average size equal to 3 μm were found at pH 10 for which the Fe₃O₄ MPs displayed the highest (absolute) zeta potential value. The

aggregation process was expected (and desired from the electroanalytical point of view) since no capping agent was used during the Fe_3O_4 synthesis. Such processing conditions lead to the formation of assemblies, aggregates, and ultimately larger objects reaching μm sizes[45]. We decided not to perform SEM/TEM analysis as the magnetic nature of the studied material is not suitable for the intended instruments (high risk of contamination) and the overall process of the Fe_3O_4 synthesis is based on the already published protocol.

3.4. Interfacial behavior of Fe_3O_4 particles at the ITIES

The interfacial behavior of magnetic Fe_3O_4 particles was investigated at the ITIES with the aqueous phase pH set to 2.0, 5.5, and 10.0. BRB buffer was used as the aqueous phase for pH 2.0 and 10.0, while pH 5.5 was established using 10 mM NaCl solution (pH deviating from 7.0 is due to CO_2 dissolution). The organic phase was always 5 mM BTTPATPBCl dissolved in 1,2-DCE. After pouring the aqueous on top of the organic phase, an interface was formed. Afterward, the desired quantity of magnetic particles was injected with a micropipette into the aqueous phase of the LLI. CVs were recorded before and after the addition of magnetic particles, leading to a conclusion that in the studied particle concentration range blank readings (in the absence of magnetic particles), do not display any additional charge transfer reactions, happening within the available potential difference scale for which the LLI is polarized (see Fig. 2). However, the addition of Fe_3O_4 particles slightly narrowed the potential window from the positive end, which is limited by cations transfer from the aqueous to the organic phase (positive currents) and their back transfer from the organic to aqueous phase – negative current. In practice these are Na^+ and H^+ transferring from the aqueous to organic phase at the $\text{pH} > 5.5$ and $\text{pH} < 5.5$, respectively. We have also observed that the peak current magnitudes at the far positive end of voltammograms slightly increased with increasing concentration of Fe_3O_4 . The shift of the positive end to lower potential difference values and increased current attributed to magnetic particles presence may indicate the presence of other charge transfer mechanisms, presumably facilitated ion transfer. The increase in the current signal of Na^+ transfer at the far end of the CV was previously studied at the water|1,2-dichlorobenzene interface by Al Nasser *et al.*[22]. By adding ionophore dibenzo-18-crown-6 (DB18C6) to the organic phase in the presence of 2D molybdenum disulfide (MoS_2) nanosheets, Na^+ facilitated transfer was studied. As a result, the presence of MoS_2 nanosheets, enhanced its transfer and increased current intensity as studied by cyclic voltammetry[22]. This also occurred

in the presence of Au nanoparticles[28], cobalt magnetic nanoparticles[34] and FePd ferromagnetic nanowires[46]. Recently, Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles coated with two different polymers, chitosan and diethylaminoethyl dextran were studied as the LLI modifiers [36,37]. It was found, that the nature of the capping agent can affect the interaction between particles and studied analytes. Such behavior can be explained by the existence of electrostatic and hydrophobic interactions occurring between the core of the particle, the particle surface (properties governed by capping agent), and ions existing in both phases. In our case, we have found that the effect of the magnetic particle addition (bare, without capping agent) mostly affects the shape of the voltammogram for the higher potential difference values. The capacitive current recorded in CVs from Fig. 2 in the potential range where no Faradaic reactions occurred after addition of Fe₃O₄ did not display any significant changes. We have also used the AC Voltammetry (see Fig. S4 from ESI) to specifically probe the differential capacitance of the interfacial region after the addition of studied particles. It was shown by a few group that this technique is especially useful to investigate the change in the interfacial electrical properties in the presence of adsorbed materials[31,47]. AC voltammograms confirm that the adsorption of Fe₃O₄ occur since (i) at pH 2.0 we observed the shift in the potential of zero charge by around 30 mV towards lower potential value after magnetic particles addition and increase in the differential capacitance in the more positive potential range (around 2 $\mu\text{F}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$); (ii) very small shift in the potential of zero charge at pH = 5.5 and (iii) nearly no changes in differential capacitance close to the potential of zero charge at pH = 10.0. These findings indicate that although the adsorption of Fe₃O₄ is pH and applied-dependent, the changes in the differential capacitance of the LLI are rather small.

Figure 2. CVs recorded for the increasing concentrations of Fe₃O₄ particles initially added to the aqueous phase of the LLI configuration. The pH of the aqueous phase was 2.0 (A), 5.5 (B) and 10.0 (C). BRB buffer was used as the aqueous phase for pH 2.0 and 10.0, while 10 mM NaCl solution pH was equal to 5.5. The scan rate was 20 mV·s⁻¹. Forward polarization: from low to high potential difference values.

3.5. Interfacial behavior of TMA⁺ and OBS⁻

To analyze the effect of the presence of Fe₃O₄ particles at the water|1,2 DCE interface, two model ions were selected. Namely, the anion 4-octylbenzenesulfonate (OBS⁻) used as the sodium salt and the cation, tetramethylammonium (TMA⁺) chloride salt, were chosen to study their interfacial behavior at the ITIES in the presence and the absence of Fe₃O₄ particles. In all pH values investigated in our study, the selected ions, TMA⁺ and OBS⁻, are positively and negatively charged, respectively. As previously described, our Fe₃O₄ magnetic particles are positively charged at pH 2.0, negatively charged around pH 5.5, and strongly negatively charged at pH 10.0[1]. The isoelectric point of magnetic iron oxide nanoparticles is around pH 6.8[1,48]. The interactions of particles with OBS⁻ and TMA⁺ were studied with CV. Fig. 3 shows CVs recorded for increasing concentrations of magnetic particles added to a fixed concentration of 50 μM OBS⁻ always initially present in the aqueous phase. Here, the forward scan progressed from positive to negative potential. The negative currents correspond to the transfer of OBS⁻ from the aqueous to the organic phase, while the positive currents are its back transfer from the organic to the aqueous phase. The current intensities assigned to OBS⁻ ion transfer are calculated as the height of the current signal recorded on the voltammograms after background current subtraction. The current intensities trends of OBS⁻ ion transfer after increasing concentrations of Fe₃O₄ particles at different pH values are shown in Fig. 3D - 3F. It can be observed that the addition of particles results in an increase in both positive and negative current intensities, which is dependent on the MPs concentration. However, a higher amount of particles reverse this trend as shown in Fig. 3D-3F. The forward peak current intensities increased by 2.38 μA for 1.00 mg·mL⁻¹ addition of MPs, 6.10 μA for 7.75 mg·mL⁻¹ addition of MPs, and 3.66 μA for 3.98 mg·mL⁻¹ addition for pH 2.0, 5.5, and 10, respectively. However, the observed trend was found to reverse as the concentration of MPs further increased (Fig. 3). This could be explained by LLI saturation with MPs, Fe₃O₄ accumulated and aggregated at the interface,

hence retarding the ion transfer. It is important to note that MPs increased current intensities (up to their certain concentration as indicated above) in all pH conditions studied for OBS^- ion transfer.

Figure 3. CVs recorded for the increasing concentration of Fe_3O_4 particles added to the aqueous phase being a solution of 50 μM 4-octylbenzenesulfonic anion at pH = 2.0 (A), pH = 5.5 (B), pH = 10.0 (C). The current intensities are plotted in function of Fe_3O_4 particle concentration at pH = 2.0 (D), pH = 5.5 (E), pH = 10.0 (F). A BRB buffer in 10 mM NaCl with a pH of 2.0 and 10.0 was used as the aqueous phase, while a 10 mM NaCl was used for pH 5.5. Forward polarization: from high to low potential difference values.

The second studied model ion was TMA^+ as shown in SI Fig. S3. For the pH value equal to 5.5, the overall current dropping behavior was found, both for the forward and reversed peak current (forward is attributed to the transfer of TMA^+ from the aqueous to the organic phase) as the concentration of MPs was increasing - see SI Fig. S4B. In turn, at pH 2.0, and 10.0, both positive and negative signals provided current – MPs concentration patterns similar to that recorded for OBS^- - initial current intensity increase followed by gradual drop.

At a pH of 2, the addition of 2 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ of MPs to the aqueous phase resulted in a maximum current response elevated by around 1.00 and 2.6 μA for positive and negative peak current intensities, respectively. At a pH of 10.0, the addition of 0.4 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ of Fe_3O_4 particles resulted in a maximum

current increase equal to 1.8 and 2.5 μA for positive and negative currents, consecutively. Since TMA^+ and OBS^- displayed similar current – MPs concentration dependency we believe that initially, particles contribute to the increasing surface area of the electrified LLI (formation of the three-dimensional structure of the particles wetted by aqueous phase – the iron oxide covered surface contact angles were found to be as low as 17° to further[49], this is at higher concentration, physically block soft junction. We have noticed that the fixed vertex potential for CVs recorded at different pH values affect the blank reading (the current memory due to the background ion transfer reactions) as such affecting the calculated value of the peak intensity attributed to the TMA^+ and OBS^- . This is why, the data sets from Fig. 3 and Fig. S3 should be interpreted as dependencies of how the presence of Fe_3O_4 particles affect the interfacial behavior of studied ions at particular pH. Corresponding data sets are also dispelled in the normalized manner (normalization was done to the first data point extracted from the voltammograms recorded in the absence of magnetic particles) as shown in Fig. S5.

The calibration curves for OBS^- ion transfer were plotted using positive and negative signals obtained from CVs. Fig. 4 presents the calibration curves for OBS^- plotted based on the CVs analysis recorded in the absence and presence of MPs at different pH values. The peak current for OBS^- transfer from the aqueous to the organic phase and during the reversed scan (positive currents) increased linearly in the studied concentration range from 10 μM to 200 μM at pH 5.5, and 10. At the pH = 2.0 we show the concentration range from 10 μM to 150 μM since the addition of MPs triggered the phenomenon known in the literature as electrochemistry instability (manifested by the irregular current spikes). This phenomenon has been documented in the presence of surface-active species and studied in detail by Kakiuchi *et al.* [50]. Since nanomaterials can also act as the analogs to molecular surfactants (e.g. Pickering emulsions) it is not surprising that such destabilization was observed. Consequently, we were unable to calculate current intensities above 150 μM addition of OBS^- . In the absence of MPs, the ratio of forward and backward signals for all studied pH is close to unity (the slope of positive and negative current calibration curve of OBS^- at pH = 2.0; $I^+ (0.211)/I^- (0.246) = 0.85$; pH 5.5 $I^+ (0.126)/I^- (0.122)=1.03$; pH 10 $I^+ (0.168)/I^- (0.181)=0.93$. After the addition of MPs this ratio dropped to 0.72 and 0.76 for pH 2 and 5.5, respectively, and remained at the same level (0.96) for pH = 10. The lowering ratio between forward and reversed current indicates a higher mass transfer of OBS^- from the aqueous to the

organic phase, which in turn may indicate the preadsorption of the anion within a layer of MPs formed at the LLI.

Finally, for all studied pH values we have found that addition of MPs improved the voltammetric detection sensitivity as summarized in Table 1. At the bare interface, the sensitivity values were 0.21 and $-0.25 \text{ A}\cdot\text{M}^{-1}$ for pH 2.0, 0.13 and $-0.12 \text{ A}\cdot\text{M}^{-1}$ for pH 5.5, and 0.17 and $-0.18 \text{ A}\cdot\text{M}^{-1}$ for pH 10.0. After LLI modification with MPs slopes of the obtained calibration curves increased to, for pH 2.0 were 0.23 and $-0.33 \text{ A}\cdot\text{M}^{-1}$, for pH 5.5 were 0.17 and $-0.22 \text{ A}\cdot\text{M}^{-1}$, and for pH 10 were 0.21 and $-0.22 \text{ A}\cdot\text{M}^{-1}$. Here, the highest relative increase was found for pH 2 and 5.5 for negative signals further indicating possible preconcentration of OBS^- within MPs deposit. Since OBS^- is negatively charged within the entire conventional pH range whereas the Fe_3O_4 particles display weak negatively charged zeta potential (a few mV is characteristic for particles undergoing rapid aggregation reactions) such interactions are possible.

Figure 4. Typical CVs recorded for 100 μM of OBS^- before and after the addition of 2.05 mg/mL Fe_3O_4 MPs at pH = 2.0 (A), pH = 5.5 (B), and pH = 10.0 (C). Calibration curves obtained from CVs recorded for the increasing concentration of OBS^- in the presence and absence of 2.05 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ Fe_3O_4 MPs at pH=2.0 (D), pH=5.5 (E), and pH=10.0 (F). Forward polarization: from high to low potential difference values.

The sensitivity of TMA⁺ ion voltammetric detection was also studied at the bare and Fe₃O₄-modified LLI. Fig. 5 shows the CVs along with the corresponding calibration curves plotted for increasing concentration of TMA⁺ at bare and MPs modified LLI. At the bare interface, the sensitivity was equal to 0.16 A·M⁻¹ at pH 2.0, 0.18 A·M⁻¹ at pH 5.5, and 0.18 A·M⁻¹ at pH 10, for the positive current signals (the one attributed to the TMA⁺ transfer from the aqueous to the organic phase). When the interface was modified with Fe₃O₄ MPs, the voltammetric sensitivity for the indicated pH values slightly increased to 0.18 A·M⁻¹ at pH 2.0. For pH 5.5 it dropped to 0.16 A·M⁻¹ and remained the same, this is 0.18 A·M⁻¹ at pH 10, respectively. It is interesting to see that the interaction between TMA⁺ and MPs layer formed at the eLLI is not as prominent as in the case of OBS⁻.

Figure 5. Typical CVs recorded for 100 μM TMA⁺ before and after the addition of 2.05 mg·mL⁻¹ Fe₃O₄ particles added at pH = 2.0 (A), pH = 5.5 (B), and pH = 10.0 (C). Calibration curves obtained from CVs recorded for increasing concentration of TMA⁺ in the presence and absence of 2.05 mg·mL⁻¹ Fe₃O₄ particles at pH=2.0 (D), pH=5.5 (E), and pH=10.0 (F). Forward polarization: from low to high potential difference values.

We further calculated other electroanalytical parameters using linear fit equations obtained from both, positive and negative calibration curves. The calculated LOD and LOQ values for OBS⁻ and

TMA⁺ transfer across the bare and modified LLI with Fe₃O₄ MPs are summarized in Table 1, based on the corresponding linear fit parameters and follow-up equations:

$$LOD = \frac{3.3 \cdot SD}{S} \quad (1)$$

$$LOQ = \frac{10 \cdot SD}{S} \quad (2)$$

where, SD stands for the standard deviation of the intercept and S is a slope of a linear fit equation. In all pH ranges studied, the LOD and LOQ values both for TMA⁺ and OBS⁻ in the presence of Fe₃O₄ MPs hold the same order of magnitude as compared with non-modified LLI. This further indicates that the variations observed in terms of changing sensitivity (slope of the calibration curve) may originate from the increase in the electrochemical surface area after Fe₃O₄ particles interfacial absorption combined with the specific interactions between particles and studied molecules.

Table 1. The summary of electroanalytical parameters obtained for OBS⁻ and TMA⁺ in the presence and absence of 2.05 mg.ml⁻¹ at different pH of the aqueous phase.

Analyte		Slope	Slope	LOD	LOD	LOQ	LOQ	pH
		(+) / A·M ⁻¹	(-) / A·M ⁻¹	(+) / μM	(-) / μM	(+) / μM	(-) / μM	
OBS ⁻	Bare	0.21	0.25	7.69	1.3	23.3	4.0	2
	Fe ₃ O ₄	0.23	0.33	6.54	5.2	19.8	15.7	
	Bare	0.13	0.12	4.53	3.3	13.7	10.0	5.5
	Fe ₃ O ₄	0.17	0.22	12.56	11.4	38.1	34.4	
	Bare	0.17	0.18	7.11	6.1	21.6	18.5	10
	Fe ₃ O ₄	0.21	0.22	9.4	7.1	28.4	21.4	
TMA ⁺	Bare	0.16	0.20	10.4	4.6	31.6	13.8	2

Fe₃O₄	0.18	0.22	11.7	7.2	35.3	21.9	5.5
Bare	0.18	0.19	10.2	5.3	30.1	16.1	
Fe₃O₄	0.16	0.16	7.6	5.0	23.0	15.2	10
Bare	0.18	0.20	5.5	5.0	16.6	15.3	
Fe₃O₄	0.18	0.20	5.7	5.2	17.3	15.7	

3.6. Interfacial behavior of levamisole drug

Levamisole hydrochloride drug was chosen for experimental validation of the electroanalytical protocol involving the utilization of Fe₃O₄ MPs as the LLI modified. Levamisole is known as an anthelmintic drug approved for use in veterinary medicine. Previously, it was used in human medicine as an immunomodulator in rheumatoid arthritis and colorectal cancer therapy[51]. Additionally; it is employed as an adulterant in illicit drug preparations due to its white powder color[52]. Hence, the protocols allowing its rapid detection are needed. As in the case of TMA⁺ and 4-OBS⁻, CV was used to assess the effect of Fe₃O₄ MPs presence and the aqueous phase pH on the electroanalytical parameters attributed to the levamisole detection, and the obtained results are shown in Fig. 6. Initially, at the pH 2.0 or 5.5, addition of Fe₃O₄ MPs did not increase current intensities attributed to levamisole ion transfer (data not shown). At a pH of 10.0, an increase in positive and negative current was observed when the LLI was modified with Fe₃O₄ particles as shown in Fig.6C.

This value is very close to levamisole pK_a which is 8[53], and hence indicates that in the aqueous phase levamisole will have a fraction of species being positively charged and a fraction of species holding zero net charge. Eventual interaction between the drug and Fe₃O₄ particles should be dominated by electrostatic interactions (between the positive charge species of levamisole and the surface charge of Fe₃O₄ MPs that is negative at pH of 10.0). Levamisole hydrochloride was electroanalytically studied in the presence and absence of Fe₃O₄ in two different ways. First, the CVs were recorded when the interface was modified with Fe₃O₄, and the concentration of levamisole was increased using the same cell throughout the experiment (method 1). The results

are shown in Fig. 6A. In the second approach, seven cells, each being a solution of increasing levamisole concentration were used to study the effect of MPs on the resulting ion transfer currents attributed to the analyte of interest (method 2). The calibration curve for the latter method is shown in Fig. 6B.

Figure 6. (A and B) Calibration curve obtained from CVs measurement with increasing concentration of levamisole hydrochloride in the presence and absence of 2.05 mg·mL⁻¹ Fe₃O₄ MPs. For A all points were recorded in the single cell, for B each point is a single experiment. Typical CVs recorded for 100 μM levamisole hydrochloride before and after the addition of 2.05 mg·mL⁻¹ Fe₃O₄ particles (C). Aqueous phase pH was set to 10.0. Leva stands for levamisole. Forward polarization: from low to high potential difference values.

For the first applied methodology, we did not observe improved voltammetric detection sensitivity which was surprising given that the current intensity attributed to the levamisole ion transfer initially (directly after Fe₃O₄ MPs addition) increased as shown in Fig. 6C. Here LOD and LOQ were higher in the presence of MPs compared to bare interface. In turn, when we applied second methodology, we have found that the detection sensitivity increased after MPs addition. In this type of experiment, we always assess the effect of the MPs based on the comparison with the blank reading (defined as the CVs recorded before MPs addition) recorded in the investigated cell. For levamisole detection, the obtained sensitivity values are summarized in Table 2 along with LOD and LOQ values. The latter values were lower compared to the bare interface. Performed experiments indicate that increased ion transfer signals recorded in the presence of levamisole can be only recorded during the first few voltammetric scans which may indicate MPs saturation process and potential necessity of the formed surface renewal.

Table 2. Electroanalytical values of levamisole drug in the presence and absence of 2.05 mg.ml⁻¹ at pH 10 in both cells 1 and 2. The unit of sensitivity is A·M⁻¹.

Method	Modification	Sensitivity (+) / A·M ⁻¹	Sensitivity (-) / A·M ⁻¹	LOD(+) μM	LOD(-) μM	LOQ(+) μM	LOQ(-) μM
Method 1	Bare	0.21	0.21	4.32	3.96	13.12	12.00
	Fe₃O₄	0.22	0.23	11.56	9.05	35.04	27.43
Method 2	Bare	0.14	0.12	27.74	23.16	84.05	70.18
	Fe₃O₄	0.21	0.19	17.97	14.09	54.47	42.69

Conclusion

In this work, we have studied the electroanalytical properties of the liquid-liquid interface modified with the Fe₃O₄ magnetic particles. It is important to note that particles were deprived from the capping agent, and hence, undergo rapid aggregation in the aqueous phase followed by sedimentation at the LLI. The zeta potential and size of the particles were evaluated at different pH values (2.0; 5.5 and 10.0). The interfacial behavior of these magnetic particles was studied using a macroscopic four-electrode cell. We have found that initial particle addition to the aqueous phase (low concentration) results in the current response increase as studied with model ions (TMA⁺ and OBS⁻). This observation is mainly attributed to the increasing surface area of contact between the two phases and electrostatic interactions. Further, an increase in the Fe₃O₄ concentration was always followed by a dropping ionic current most probably due to the existence of physical obstacles encountered by ions undergoing interfacial ion transfer processes. The Fe₃O₄ concentration assuring the highest current response was chosen, and the calibration curves were built for model ions. These in turn indicated elevated voltammetric sensitivity values with a 2-fold increase for the OBS⁻ at pH 5.5. Finally, the Fe₃O₄-based LLI modification was employed to electroanalytical study the interfacial behavior of levamisole (a molecule frequently used as an illicit drug street sample cutting agent). We have optimized the conditions for levamisole detection by increasing voltammetric detection sensitivity from 0.14 to 0.21 A·M⁻¹.

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Data availability statement

Raw data are uploaded to the scientific repository and are available under DOI:10.5281/zenodo.13310752.

Conflict of interests

Authors declare no conflict of interests.

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